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Research Article

**ETHICAL ISSUES FACED BY NURSES DURING NURSING
PRACTICE IN PAKISTAN**Naziran Batool¹, Bushra Rehmat², Tahira Shaheen³¹Head Nurse, Children Hospital Lahore²Head Nurse, Lady Willingdon Hospital, Lahore³Nursing instructor, Post Graduate College of Nursing Punjab, Lahore**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: An ethical issue can arise in any healthcare situation where profound moral questions of “right” or “wrong” underlie professional decision-making and the care of patients. **Objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the ethical issues faced by nurses during nursing practice in Pakistan. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Children Hospital Lahore during March 2019 to November 2019. The data was collected from 125 nurses of the hospital, which were selected randomly. The data was collected through systematically designed questionnaire. **Results:** The data was collected from 125 patients. The majority of respondents reported frequently or daily encountering issues related to protecting patients' rights (63.9%) and informed consent to treatment procedures (61.3%). Everyday encounters were also common with advanced care planning (41%), difficult staffing patterns (37.3%) surrogate decision-making (32.5%) and end-of life (26.2%) issues; respondents less frequently reported experiencing breaches of patient confidentiality and unethical practices. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that nurses were aware about their ethical responsibilities but were often unable to practice them.

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INTRODUCTION:

An ethical issue can arise in any healthcare situation where profound moral questions of “right” or “wrong” underlie professional decision-making and the care of patients. Health professionals especially nurses face ethical challenges in their daily practice as they are required to provide autonomous and collaborative care to individuals of all ages, while adhering to the ethical principles [1]. The situation becomes particularly complex for nurses who work under severe resource constraints. Additionally due to the demographic, social, scientific and technological aspects of health care, there has been an increase in complexity of ethical issues faced in the health care service delivery. Ethical issues in the nursing practice attract little attention, resulting in the creation of moral distress, poor professional care, unproductivity and conflict [2].

Nurses everywhere have long struggled with ethical challenges in patient care. In fact, in Florence Nightingale's *Notes on Nursing*, she discussed ethical duties of confidentiality, communication, and the centrality of meeting patients' needs. Similarly, nurses today are bound to uphold the foundational moral virtues, duties and principles central to the nursing profession [3]. However, it has become increasingly difficult for nurses in all parts of the world to practise with integrity amidst the complex moral choices and pressures that nurses confront [4].

Today's healthcare environment is demanding for nurses at a time when there is a critical shortage of staff to meet the multifaceted needs of patients. An ethical issue can occur in any healthcare situation where profound moral questions of “rightness” or “wrongness” underlie professional decision-making and the beneficent care of patients [5]. For example, critical care nurses often face suffering head-on, and might question the balance between the value of attempts to preserve a patient's life and aggressive physiological measures that appear to prolong anguish

and yield no fruitful outcome. Understandably, all members of the healthcare team, including nurses, can be affected by ethical decisions as they address the stressful and sometimes exhausting nature of working through ethical problems [6].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the ethical issues faced by nurses during nursing practice in Pakistan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Children Hospital Lahore during March 2019 to November 2019. The data was collected from 125 nurses of the hospital, which were selected randomly. The data was collected through systematically designed questionnaire. This questionnaire include socio demographic values and questions related to ethical issues faces by the nurses of the hospital. Socio-demographic variables examined included age, gender, income, practice setting, years in practice, years in position, level of education, ethics education, and state of practice.

Data were analysed using SPSS version 19. Descriptive statistics included frequencies, means, standard deviations, and medians.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 125 patients. The majority of respondents reported frequently or daily encountering issues related to protecting patients' rights (63.9%) and informed consent to treatment procedures (61.3%). Everyday encounters were also common with advanced care planning (41%), difficult staffing patterns (37.3%) surrogate decision-making (32.5%) and end-of life (26.2%) issues; respondents less frequently reported experiencing breaches of patient confidentiality and unethical practices.

Table 01: Frequency of stress related to ethical issues

Ethical and Patient Care Issue	Frequency		
	Frequently or Daily (%)	Sometimes (%)	Never or Seldom (%)
Protecting patients' rights	63.9	21.5	14.5
Autonomy and informed consent to treatment	61.3	21.1	17.7
Breaches of patient confidentiality or right to privacy	23.2	26.4	50.4
Unethical practices of health professionals	6.8	21.3	72.0
Provider rights and duties	19.9	20.6	59.6
Beginning-of-life decision-making	8.0	7.5	84.5
Conflicts of interest	13.3	29.3	57.4
Medical research, therapeutic innovation, or experimental treatment and related issues	10.5	17.8	71.7
Resource allocation	10.4	19.3	70.4
Conflicting professional obligations to patient, institution, and/or profession	9.7	27.8	62.5
Staffing patterns that negatively affect work	37.3	31.8	30.8

Table 02: Degree of stress related to ethical issues

Degree of Stress		
High or Very High (%)	Moderate (%)	None or Low (%)
12.3	28.7	58.9

DISCUSSION:

In this study nurses underscored the problems encountered during hospital admissions of patients with obstetrical emergency when doctors were not available. This finding is consistent with a facility based study conducted by Shamshad et al. in Pakistan which indicated that most of the maternal deaths in hospital admitted patient were preventable and could be prevented by provision of skilled care and timely management of complications [7]. Report of American Association of Retired Person Public Policy Institute, recognized similar barriers in another setting and allowed Advanced Practice Registered Nurse Practitioners (APRNs) hospital privileges which resulted in benefits to consumers and improved the health care delivery system especially for Medicare patients [8]. Such measures potentially decreased costs and expedited treatment by eliminating the need for physician to sign-off on every service provided. This improved the quality of services as the physicians then could focus on specialized services. Based on the same principle Ontario Hospital Association in its guidelines, enabled the registered nurse practitioners to have privileges to admit and discharge patient. Given the shortage of skilled health care professionals in Pakistan, similar privileges to registered nursing professionals may help improve quality of healthcare services. Jafree et al. have reported problems due to patient preferences and informed consent from female patients as identified in the current study [9].

The most frequently voiced issue was the inequitable workload. There was high turnover of patients and less number of nurses available. These findings are similar to those identified by Hussain and Buchan. Another contributing factor identified in the current study was the pressure exerted on nurses by influential patients to attend to their needs on priority, which further hindered equitable patient care [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that nurses were aware about their ethical responsibilities but were often unable to practice them. The findings showed that nurses were not the decision makers in many situations; they were subordinates in their working environment.

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